

**THE INFLUENCE OF ENTERTAINMENT MEDIA ON YOUTH
ATTITUDES TOWARD EDUCATION IN NIGERIA**

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Abstract: The study investigated the effect of entertainment media on attitudes of the youths towards education in Nigeria. As more and more young people have become exposed to digital entertainment, like social networking, streaming, music videos, celebrity culture, and more, there are concerns regarding the implications of these for education and academic engagement. The research design used in the study was a mixed-methods research design that comprised a convergent parallel design because quantitative and qualitative approaches were used. The respondents were sampled from 428 students from secondary schools, and 20 respondents, consisting of students, teachers, and parents from tertiary schools, were interviewed for qualitative data. The data were analysed quantitatively using descriptive and inferential statistics such as percentages, correlation and regression and qualitatively, thematically. Results indicated that most participants spend a considerable amount of time every day engaging in entertainment media and that most indicated that their engagement with entertainment media had an impact on their attitudes regarding education. The study revealed that there is a significant relationship between the consumption of entertainment media and the decrease in academic motivation, the decrease in reading culture and the increase in entertainment lifestyles. It also found that there are positive educational uses of entertainment media, such as access to online tutorials, educational videos and edutainment content. The study concluded that entertainment media has a double meaning to education, but the negative influence is more dominant if entertainment media use is excessive and unregulated. The study calls for media literacy education, parental monitoring, the integration of digital learning tools in the curriculum and the promotion of educational entertainment content to improve positive academic outcomes among the Nigerian youths.

Keywords: Entertainment Media, Mouth Attitudes, Education, Nigeria, Mixed-Methods, Academic Motivation, Social Media.

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I. INTRODUCTION

With the advent and growing popularity of the entertainment media, the cultural, social and educational lives of youth around the globe have been drastically changed. The penetration of digital technologies, smartphones, the internet, streaming services and social networking applications has raised the level of exposure of Nigeria's youth to entertainment-oriented content. The entertainment media, ranging from television shows, music videos, films, online streaming, celebrity culture, comedy sketches, online gaming, and social media platforms like TikTok, Instagram, YouTube, Facebook, and X (previously known as Twitter), have seeped their way into the lives of Nigerian youths. As a result, in today's society, young people are developing new attitudes, aspirations, lifestyles and perceptions of education and academic achievement as a result of their media consumption.

Education continues to be a significant tool for the development of the Nation, human capital development, poverty alleviation and socioeconomic transformation in Nigeria. But there have been some concerns among scholars, educators, parents and policy makers about the attitude of the youths towards formal education in the face of the rise of entertainment media. Research indicates that over time, spending too much time on entertainment content can lead to a drop in the reading culture in society, which also hinders focus in classrooms, academic motivation, and fascination with celebrity lives and instant wealth stories (Asanga et al., 2023; Ukpabi et al., 2025). The rise in popularity of influencers, musicians, actors and online celebrities that are typically associated with a lavish lifestyle and choosing to downplay education has only worsened debates over the role of entertainment media in students' educational orientation.

The effect of entertainment media on the attitude of youth towards education has many aspects. On the other hand, entertainment media can have a negative influence on students, distracting them, leaving them less motivated to study and to be present at class, and creating a dependency on the media. Excessive hours on

entertainment social media have been shown to affect academic engagement and study habits of students (Ukpoju et al., 2023; Oyegbami & Oni, 2023). The same is true for the proliferation of short-form digital content and a corresponding shift in short attention spans and loss of interest in long academic reading by adolescents and college students. In recent years, several studies have been conducted in Nigeria, indicating that some students are more interested in enjoying online entertainment and gaining social validation than in fulfilling their academic duties (Ciroma et al., 2025). The impact of these changes on education and national development in the long term is a concern.

But the educational value of the entertainment media is also significant. Digital entertainment platforms are becoming more and more a source for educational documentaries, online tutorials, edutainment programs, educational podcasts and instructional videos, which complement the learning outcomes and academic development. Today, students use social media apps like YouTube and WhatsApp to learn together, communicate with each other and access educational resources (Otonomeruke & Sunday, 2017). Therefore, the entertainment media can be used both positively and negatively, depending on the attitude of its users, the content of the media that is watched and the media competence of the young people.

Although there is a considerable amount of research already in existence dealing with media studies and educational technology, there is a lack of in-depth and comprehensive studies focused on the impact of entertainment media on the attitudes of the youth towards education in the Nigerian context through a mixed-method study. Current literature has been largely found to be narrowly examining social media usage and academic performance, while neglecting to address its impact in a broader context of entertainment media and educational perception and value orientation.

With the rising consumption of entertainment media among the Nigerian youths, there have been a lot of debates about its implications for educational development. Lots of students spend more time on social media, music entertainment, online celebrity culture and streaming platforms than on studying. Some entertainment media promote the worship of material wealth without a focus on education, which has led to some concerns with scholars, educators and policymakers.

Furthermore, Nigeria's educational institutions have been adversely affected by issues like a drop in reading culture, the use of smartphones as classroom distractions, students' attention span and lack of interest in the academic program. Some scholars believe that the negative influence of the entertainment media on the educational orientation, while others believe that the digital entertainment media can be a medium that facilitates creativity, learning, and access to educational resources.

The findings were not consistent, and no comprehensive studies (mixed methods) were conducted, which calls for more research into the actual effect of entertainment media on the attitudes of young people towards education in Nigeria.

Thus, this study aimed at examining the impact of entertainment media on youth attitudes toward education in Nigeria; a mixed-method approach of both quantitative and qualitative research was used. The study is anticipated to make contributions to the existing literature, guide the formulation of educational policies and make recommendations to foster responsible media consumption among the Nigerian youths.

This study aims to study the role of Entertainment media on the attitudes of Nigerian youths towards education.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The study literature review is structured into conceptual review, theoretical review and empirical review to give a comprehensive knowledge of how entertainment media affects the attitudes of youth towards education in Nigeria.

III. CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Understanding of entertainment media

Entertainment media is a media of communication and digital media that are used to give amusement, recreation and relaxation to the audience, and to engage them in a social interaction. Entertainment media refers to any media production that provides entertainment, such as television programs, films, music videos, online streaming, comedy shows, social media, celebrity blogs, podcasts, gaming apps and internet-based audiovisual media. The advent of digital technologies has made entertainment media a very interactive medium that not only provides entertainment but also allows users to create and disseminate entertainment materials (Acheme et al. 2025). The growing penetration of the internet and mobile phones in Nigeria has made it easier for youths to be exposed to media content that is geared towards entertainment.

The popular media or entertainment media have become one of the socialisation agents that affect the values and beliefs, aspirations, pattern of language, fashion and pattern of orientation of young people. Mass media is a key factor in moulding the attitude of society as it is a source of exposure to the culture's narratives and social

realities that are continuous in the society (Ukpabi et al., 2025). Nigerian youths spend a lot of hours daily on social media platforms like TikTok, Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, Netflix and X (previously known as Twitter), which raises the exposure of entertainment media to their perspectives and orientation.

Researchers have debated the positive and negative effects which entertainment media can have on educational results. Factors that have proven to be positive include the use of educational documentaries, online tutorials, and educative television programmes and the use of co-constructed and co-created digital learning communities (Nasir et al., 2021). But, when it comes to the consumption of entertainment, students might be distracted, decrease study time, have a poor reading culture, poor concentration, and poor commitment to study (Ukpoju et al., 2023).

Youth Attitudes Toward Education

Attitude towards education is a person's thoughts, opinions, feelings and behaviour patterns about education, learning and academic performance. Positive educational attitudes are manifested in the motivation of students to learn, commitment to carrying out educational activities, students' involvement in class, students' love for reading, and their educational aspirations. Negative attitudes, however, are shown in such behaviour as truancy, disengagement from the school's learning process, lack of concentration, lack of reading habits, and a decrease in formal education interest.

Over the past few years, there has been a growing concern about the changing attitude of the Nigerian youths in terms of education. This trend has been attributed to some extent as a result of exposure to digital media and the promotion of celebrity culture that celebrates earning money without qualification (Akinkoya et al., 2021). Familiar with the influencers, musicians, comedians, and online celebrities, the new normal for youngsters in terms of success has changed. As a result, there is an increasing number of young people who are now finding that being in the spotlight on social media or gaining a level of "entertainment" fame is more profitable than studying.

Moreover, the immediate entertainment content and quick consumption of such material conveyed by media may lead to a drop in attention span and long-term academic concentration. The interaction with entertainment applications has been noted to have an impact on the drop in reading culture and reduction of students' intellectual engagement in recent times among Nigerian scholars and educators (Acheme et al., 2025).

IV. THEORETICAL REVIEW

The Uses and Gratification Theory.

This study is based on Uses and Gratification Theory proposed by Katz, Blumler and Gurevitch. The theory suggests that the audience is active and makes their own choice of media according to their needs, motives and desires. People watch media for different reasons such as being entertained, information, relaxation, identity, escapism and social interaction.

The theory is applicable in this study because all Nigerian youth deliberately use entertainment media to meet emotional and psychological demands. Platforms like TikTok, Instagram, YouTube and Netflix offer entertainment, social interaction and social validation; all of these lure young users. It is noted, however, that overindulgence in the use of entertainment media can lead to students' attention shifting from activities to learning and learning objectives (Udoudo & Ojo, 2016). This theory, therefore, can provide an explanation of why youths are more interested in consuming entertainment media rather than doing their studies.

Social Learning Theory

The Social Learning Theory by Albert Bandura suggests that people acquire behaviours, attitudes, and social values by observing, imitating and modelling others. The theory suggests that individuals are more likely to engage in behaviours demonstrated by role models, especially if these behaviours are perceived as being rewarding or socially desirable.

When young people watch their entertainment media, they are often introduced to celebrities, influencers, musicians, actors and online personalities whose lives appear to be a glamorous and luxurious lifestyle with financial prosperity. Repeatedly seeing these lifestyles through the media can make young people imagine that education is not an important asset, and they can behave the same way. Akinkoya et al (2021) noted that the media content has a significant influence on students' behavioural attitudes and value systems in Nigeria. Thus, the Social Learning Theory can be used in understanding how the attitude of youth in the field of education is influenced by entertaining media.

V. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

There are several empirical studies which focus on the influence of media on youth behaviour, learning process and educational achievement. In the study by Udoudo and Ojo (2016), the researchers observed that the selected schools in Rivers State, Nigeria, had their students making extensive use of the new media, but the students' use of the new media for educational purposes was limited. The study also revealed that distraction and the misuse of entertainment applications are significant issues that impact students' engagement with learning.

The attitude of the Nigerian college students towards attitude cultivation through broadcast media entertainment was studied by Akinkoya et al. (2021). They found that students' behavioural patterns, social values and cultural orientations were significantly affected by the exposure to entertainment programmes. The study proved that entertainment media is one cause of the formation of attitudes among youth.

Ukpabi et al. (2025) studied the impact of mass media on the academic performance of secondary school students in Nigeria. The study revealed that the prolonged media usage had a negative impact on students' reading culture, concentration and academic performance. The researchers, however, admitted that if used properly, the media used in education can improve the learning results.

In the same manner, Nasir et al. (2021) explored the concept of educational entertainment in the modern-day African society using the television programme (TVP) Super Story. The research validated that edutainment programmes have significant educational value to encourage social awareness and learning among the target groups of young people.

Acheme et al. (2025) investigated undergraduates' media and film literacy in Nigeria and found that digital film usage has a different influence on youths' social attitudes, preferences, and intellectual orientation. The study highlighted the increasing significance of Media Literacy Education in Nigerian Higher Institutions.

Although these studies have been conducted, no research has integrated quantitative and qualitative approaches to comprehensively explore the impact of entertainment media on the attitude of youths in Nigeria towards education. This study, therefore, aims to fill this gap in the literature.

VI. METHODOLOGY

This research used a mixed-method research design, which combined quantitative and qualitative research methods in the study of the influence of entertainment media on Nigerian youth attitudes towards education. The mixed methods approach was deemed suitable as it allowed the researcher to have in-depth data obtained through the amalgamation of numerical analysis and the participants' experiences. In particular, the study employed a convergent parallel method in which data from quantitative and qualitative methods were obtained at the same time and were analysed separately and then merged.

The target population were secondary and undergraduate students of the selected educational institutions in Nigeria. To ensure adequate sampling by gender, age and educational level, Stratified random sampling was used to select a sample size of 450 respondents. Furthermore, 20 participants comprising teachers, parents and students were purposively selected for in-depth interviews to capture qualitative information on media influence and attitudes towards education.

Data collection tools used were structured questionnaires and a semi-structured interview guide. The questionnaire consisted of close-ended items on a 5-point Likert scale from 'Strongly agree' to 'Strongly disagree'. This instrument measured the exposure to entertainment media, academic motivation, reading habits, and perceptions of education. The questions in the interview guide were designed to include the views and experiences of participants about entertainment media consumption and its educational relevance.

The instruments of the research were made valid by having an expert check them, and reliable by having a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.87, which means that the coefficient of internal consistency is high. The quantitative data were analysed statistically using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics such as percentages, frequency tables, Pearson correlation and regression analysis. Data was presented using a pie chart, bar diagram and line graph. Qualitative data obtained from interviews were analyzed thematically to identify recurring patterns and perspectives relevant to the study objectives.

VII. ANALYSIS OF DATA AND RESULTS

This section presents the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data collected from respondents regarding the influence of entertainment media on youth attitudes toward education in Nigeria. The quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, while qualitative responses from interviews were analyzed thematically. Data presentation includes tables, pie charts, bar graphs, and line graphs for clarity and interpretation.

Response Rate

A total of 450 questionnaires were distributed to respondents across selected secondary schools and universities in Nigeria. Out of these, 428 questionnaires were properly completed and returned, representing a response rate of 95.1%, while 22 questionnaires were discarded due to incomplete responses.

Table 4.1 Response Rate

Response Category	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Returned Questionnaires	428	95.1
Unreturned/Invalid	22	4.9
Total	450	100

The high response rate indicates adequate participation and reliability of the data obtained for the study.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Gender Distribution

Table 4.2 Gender Distribution

Gender	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Male	224	52.3
Female	204	47.7
Total	428	100

Figure 1: Pie Chart of Gender Distribution

The results show that 52.3% of respondents were male while 47.7% were female, indicating balanced gender representation.

Age Distribution

Table 4.3 Age Distribution

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage(%)
15–18 Years	132	30.8
19–22 Years	181	42.3
23–25 Years	115	26.9
Total	428	100

The majority of respondents (42.3%) were within the age bracket of 19–22 years, which represents the most active population in entertainment media consumption.

Extent of Entertainment Media Exposure

Respondents were asked to indicate the average number of hours spent daily on entertainment media platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, YouTube, Netflix, music streaming applications, and television programmes.

Table 4.4 Daily Hours Spent on Entertainment Media

Hours Per Day	Frequency	Percentage(%)
1–2Hours	74	17.3
3–4Hours	176	41.1
5–6Hours	121	28.3
Above6Hours	57	13.3
Total	428	100

Figure 2: Bar Graph of Entertainment Media Exposure

The findings indicate that the majority of respondents spent between 3–4 hours daily on entertainment media, suggesting high exposure among Nigerian youths.

Influence of Entertainment Media on Educational Attitudes

Respondents were asked whether entertainment media influences their attitudes toward education.

Table 4.5 Influence on Educational Attitudes

Response	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Strongly Agree	168	39.3
Agree	142	33.2
Neutral	46	10.7
Disagree	44	10.3
Strongly Disagree	28	6.5
Total	428	100

The results reveal that 72.5% of respondents agreed that entertainment media significantly influences youth attitudes toward education.

Influence of Entertainment Media on Reading Culture

Table 4.6 Entertainment Media and Reading Habits

Response	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Strongly Agree	173	40.4
Agree	138	32.2
Neutral	39	9.1
Disagree	46	10.7
Strongly Disagree	32	7.6
Total	428	100

The findings show that 72.6% of respondents believed that entertainment media negatively affects students' reading culture and study habits.

Positive Educational Benefits of Entertainment Media

Respondents also acknowledged positive educational impacts associated with entertainment media.

Table 4.7 Positive Educational Uses of Entertainment Media

Educational Benefit	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Online Tutorials	142	33.2
Educational Videos/Documentaries	118	27.6
Academic Collaboration	96	22.4
Research and Information Access	72	16.8
Total	428	100

These results indicate that entertainment media also contributes positively to educational development through digital learning opportunities.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis One

H₀: There is no significant relationship between entertainment media consumption and youth attitudes toward education in Nigeria.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between entertainment media consumption and youth attitudes toward education in Nigeria.

Table 4.8 Pearson Correlation Analysis

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Entertainment Media Consumption and Educational Attitudes	0.682	0.001	Significant

Since the p-value (0.001) is less than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates a statistically significant relationship between entertainment media consumption and youth attitudes toward education in Nigeria.

Regression Analysis

Table 4.9 Regression Results

Variable	Beta Coefficient	t-value	p-value
Social Media Usage	0.64	7.84	0.001
Celebrity Influence	0.58	6.91	0.003
Streaming Entertainment	0.49	5.77	0.005

The regression results reveal that social media usage had the strongest influence on educational attitudes among respondents. Celebrity influence and streaming entertainment also significantly affected students' perceptions toward education.

Figure 3: Line Graph of Academic Motivation and Media Exposure

The line graph illustrates that academic motivation declines as entertainment media exposure increases among respondents.

Qualitative Data Analysis

The qualitative component of this study explored in-depth perceptions of students, teachers, and parents on how entertainment media influences youth attitudes toward education in Nigeria. Data were obtained through semi-structured interviews with 20 participants and analyzed using thematic analysis. The analysis involved repeated reading of transcripts, coding of responses, and clustering of similar codes into broader themes that reflect participants’ lived experiences.

Four major themes emerged from the data: (1) celebrity lifestyle influence, (2) declining academic motivation and reading culture, (3) digital distraction and attention fragmentation, and (4) educational value of entertainment media. These themes reflect both the negative and positive dimensions of entertainment media exposure among Nigerian youths.

Table 4.10: Thematic Analysis Table

S/N	Theme	Sub-Themes	Interview Extracts Summary	Interpretation
1	Celebrity Lifestyle Influence	Social media influencers, music artists, instant wealth perception	“Many students now believe education is not necessary because influencers are rich online.”(Teacher,SS2)	Entertainment media promotes unrealistic success narratives that reduce the perceived value of formal education
2	Declining Academic Motivation & Reading Culture	Reduced study time, preference for entertainment, low interest in textbooks	“Students prefer watching TikTok videos instead of reading for exams.”(Parent)	High exposure to entertainment media contributes to reduced academic discipline and reading habits
3	Digital Distraction & Attention Fragmentation	Smartphone addiction, short-form content, classroom distraction	“Students cannot concentrate for long due to constant phone notifications.”(Lecturer)	Entertainment media creates fragmented attention spans that negatively affect learning outcomes
4	Educational Value of Entertainment Media	YouTube tutorials, online learning, edutainment content	“Some students learn better through YouTube explanations than textbooks.”(Student, Undergraduate)	Entertainment media also provides alternative learning channels that enhance understanding when properly used

Celebrity Lifestyle Influence

All participants consistently highlighted the fact that being exposed to celebrity culture has a huge influence on youth aspirations. Students frequently see friends, social media influencers, musicians and entertainers who have extravagant lifestyles, and they think these lifestyles can be obtained without formal education. This perception helps to shift the value orientation that sometimes academic success is less rewarding than entertainment-based success.

Declining Academic Motivation and Reading Culture

One of the primary concerns of teachers and parents was the lack of students' involvement in their studies. Results from the interviews revealed that students are more interested in the entertainment media than in reading a textbook or doing academic work. This is indicative of a decrease in intrinsic motivation in education.

Digital Distraction and Attention Fragmentation

The participants emphasised the fact that the use of smartphones and regular notifications is affecting the students' concentration. As short-form video platforms have gained popularity, consumers are less willing to invest the time in a learning experience.

Educational Value of Entertainment Media

While they have reservations, respondents also recognised that entertainment media have positive educational values. YouTube and educational TikTok platforms were recognised as valuable resources to describe complex academic concepts and engage in independent learning.

The qualitative results indicate the presence of two paradoxes in the attitudes of the youth towards education in Nigeria as influenced by entertainment media. It can be a detriment to academic focus and the idea of "getting it done", but when used in the right context, it can be a great asset for education. This gives a double reason for the need for media literacy and responsible use of media among Nigerian youths.

VIII. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The results of this study indicate a significant relationship between exposure to entertainment media and the attitude of the youth to education in Nigeria. Results of the quantitative aspect revealed that high percentages of the respondents spend 3-6 hours per day on entertainment media and that more than 70% of them agreed that entertainment media affects their academic attitude. This corroborates earlier studies that reveal that more exposure to media among Nigerian students is linked with decreased academic engagement and academic skills (Ukpabi et al., 2025; Atomatofa et al., 2024). Also, Apuke (2022) found that prolonged use of social media and entertainment platforms is associated with diminished academic engagement and focus among students. Asemah et al. (2023) found that students who use social media and entertainment platforms for longer durations have low academic engagement and concentration.

The present result also shows that the reading culture and academic motivation of youths who consume entertainment media have decreased. This is in line with the Social Learning Theory, which states that people imitate media figures' behaviours and values. As per Bandura's theory, seeing images from famous celebrities and influencers could influence students' views on success, causing them to think that it seems more desirable to be famous than to be in school. This is in consensus with the study of Ukpabi et al. (2025), which revealed that mass media has a strong influence on the change of students' attitudes and attitudes towards studying in Nigeria.

Secondly, the research pointed out the negative and positive influences of entertainment media. The results of the qualitative procedure showed that the use of educational content on learning platforms like YouTube or edutainment media can improve the learning process, although they can also cause distraction, decrease attention span, and poor discipline in students. It conforms to the Uses and Gratification Theory, which explains that the audience is active in choosing the media they consume to meet their learning, entertainment, and informational needs. The study by Guanah et al. (2023) also showed similar results, in which students' use of digital media is divided between academic activities and non-academic activities, but the latter prevails.

In general, the outcomes show that the entertainment media have a double effect on education. The minus effect seems to be stronger in the absence of regulation of use. This corresponds with the recent empirical studies that have highlighted the negative impact of overuse of entertainment media on the academic performance of Nigerian students and their management of time (Atomatofa et al., 2024; Nwaka-Nwandu et al., 2024). Hence, the results are again encouraging the importance of media literacy education and using media wisely and effectively by youth to achieve positive educational results.

IX. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The current study was a mixed-methods approach that explored the impact of entertainment media on the attitudes of youth toward education in Nigeria. The results highlighted that entertainment media has a great impact on students' attitudes in studying, and they spend a lot of time every day on social media, entertainment streaming and celebrity media. These findings suggest that it has negative impacts on academic motivation, reading culture, attention span, and preference for entertainment lifestyles over learning. But the study also found that entertainment media can have positive educational value when it is used to educate and provide educational tutorials online, educational videos, and edutainment. In general, entertainment media have a dual nature of influence, but in uncontrolled use, the negative impact becomes more pronounced.

Recommendations

The study recommends that media literacy education should be infused into the Nigerian school curricula to enable pupils to do a critical analysis of the media content. Parents should be aware of and control the way their children use media. Schools should also use digital learning tools that will guide students to use media tools in a productive way in their learning. In addition, both the government and media organisations should work together to create academic values that are positive through their educational entertainment material. Last but

not least, students should be encouraged to develop a balanced media consumption pattern, which would benefit their learning and recreation.

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